

LayerFold: a Python Library to Reduce the Depth of Neural Networks

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Abstract

Large-scale models are the backbone of Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing, and their generalizability allows for transfer learning and deployment in different scenarios. However, their large size means that reducing their computational and memory demands remains a challenge. Recent research proposes to achieve “layer collapse”, a condition where multiple layers can be combined due to the collapse of non-linearities to linear operators. While this is an important discovery, most studies remain theoretical, often replacing non-linearities with simple identity functions and not providing a real implementation of the more compact architecture. Our contribution is **LayerFold**, a library that studies and implements the merging of collapsed layers. We address typical cases, from fully connected to convolutional layers, discussing constraints and prospective challenges. Our tests on edge devices reveal that merely reducing network depth does not always result in faster computation, even when GPU-equipped. This work raises important warnings and opens the door to further advances in efficient model deployment.

Keywords:

Deep learning, Layer collapse, Depth compression, Pruning, PyTorch

Metadata

1. Motivation and significance

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have revolutionized various fields by learning complex patterns from extensive datasets [1], with applications spanning computer vision [2, 3], natural language processing [4], socioeconomic indexes

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Nr.	Code metadata description	
C1	Current code version	v1.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/giommaripilo/layerfold
C3	Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	none
C4	Legal Code License	MIT-License
C5	Code versioning system used	Git
C6	Software code languages, tools, and services used	Python
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments	PyTorch
C8	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	N/A
C9	Support email for questions	giommara.pilo@telecom-paris.fr

Code metadata (mandatory).

estimation [5], and beyond [6, 7]. A key component of DNNs are the activation functions, which introduce nonlinearities and enable the modeling of complex relationships, making the DNNs universal approximators of a wide range of functions [8].

Despite their transformative impact, DNNs pose significant challenges due to their reliance on large datasets and computational resources [9], as well as their interpretability limitations [10]. Neural network compression focuses on addressing these challenges by reducing the size of DNNs and leading to a prospective reduction in memory and computation, while still maintaining competitive performance on the target downstream task. Typically composed of fully connected and convolutional layers with activation functions, recent works [11, 12, 13, 14] have studied the activation functions within these layers. A trending sub-area of research is exploring the phenomenon of *layer collapse*: after training, the non-linear activation function for some layers can be removed, making them mergeable with the next one (Fig. 1). Therefore, several studies attempt to investigate the characterization of nonlinearities between layers in DNNs [15, 16], which has been leveraged to identify and eliminate unnecessary nonlinearities [12].

The problem of removing activations without impacting DNN performance was extensively examined from a theoretical perspective. However, the challenge of implementing the folding of two consecutive layers into one after

Figure 1: Typical layer collapse schemes can remove nonlinearities between layers, suggesting that the two layers can be combined. With `LayerFold` we concretely collapse layers A and B, substituting them with an equivalent.

removing the nonlinearity has received less attention, particularly when considering the physical constraints and limitations imposed by real-world hardware.

In this work, we fill this gap by providing `LayerFold`, a handy Python library for merging consecutive layers with no activation in between. Our library enables the merging of layers in typical architectures such as ResNets [17] and Swin Transformer [18], leading to a reduction of neural network depth (and potentially to memory and computation savings, Fig. 1). Our library and experimental results aim to contribute to the ongoing effort to develop more efficient and scalable DNNs, and we hope that our findings will inform future research in this area.

Our contributions could be summarized as follows:

- We introduce the Python library `LayerFold`: starting from a collapsed configuration of a DNN, the library can obtain a more compact architecture with no change in performance and without additional fine-tuning required (Sec. 3). Using the results of input-independent analytical derivation (in Appendix A) it can perform the fusion of layers on a trained model, producing a functionally equivalent, yet more compact version of the model.
- Interestingly, we identify a case where fusion is not analytically possible, leading to an overlooked limit of layer collapse methods (Sec. 3.3).
- We provide measurements on real edge devices (Sec. 4), including Raspberry Pi 4 and Jetson Orin (which is GPU equipped), with a quantitative analysis in terms of gains after layer merging. Our results, contrary to what was expected, show that layer folding does not always lead to inference time improvements and that other factors should be taken into account, namely the specific hardware used for the computations.

We therefore highlight the need for a deeper understanding of the relationship between layer merging and computational efficiency.

2. Related works

One of the earliest layer removal strategies proposed in the literature is introduced in [12]. In this work, the authors provide a learning strategy to identify whether non-linear activations can be removed, enabling the folding of adjacent linear layers into one. This is achieved by replacing ReLU-activated layers with a Parametric ReLU (PReLU) activation where the slope for the negative side is a trainable parameter: if this slope approaches one, then the full layer collapses and the non-linearity collapses to an identity function.

Layer collapse can be also tackled by leveraging pruning: some works show that strategically removing layers during training can indeed reduce the depth without impacting the final model’s performance [11, 19]. Notably, EASIER [19] is a simple layer pruning strategy that, after one complete training and through a layer output’s entropy estimation, is able to determine which are the layers collapsing and replaces the non-linearity with an identity function. The model is then fine-tuned to recover performance. From a completely different perspective, NEPENTHE [20] shows through a mathematical derivation that layers naturally collapse when employing traditional magnitude-based unstructured pruning and proposes the design of a specific pruning approach to further ease this phenomenon. In parallel, some approaches employ activation-based structured pruning strategies, which involve ranking and estimating layer importance through techniques such as feature representation assessment, as in [21].

Focusing on groups of layers removal, other works attempt to identify in one shot the group of layers that can be removed with little to no impact on the performance. Among these, LaCoOT [22] designs an Optimal Transport-based regularization function that attempts to make input-output distribution between groups of layer collapse. If this condition is realized at the end of the training, then the full block of layers can be entirely removed with no impact on the performance. Alternative approaches also entail the development of customized block importance evaluation metrics. For example, in [23] an inter-block coupling effect is taken into account to predefine a removal rate, thereby informing block pruning decisions. Similarly, [24] propose the BlockPruner method, specifically tailored for compressing Large Language Models. By leveraging the unique architectural characteristics of these models, namely the presence of multi-head attention and multi-layer perceptron blocks, their approach utilizes a perplexity-based metric to guide block pruning.

Other works have also explored selective network linearization to reduce private inference latency, such as [14], which proposes a customized gradient-based strategy for selective ReLU linearization while maintaining prediction accuracy. Similarly, [13] seeks to remove ReLUs, leveraging an order relation between ReLUs, conditioned on their amount of contribution to the accuracy. Additionally, [25] proposes a channel-wise approach that enables significant reduction of non-linear units while maintaining similar performance, exploring the linearization of neural networks.

Unlike this works, we contribute with `Layerfold` to practically fuse the two consecutive linear layers left by the removal of the non-linearity between them. In the next section, we will present the mathematical backing of our library.

3. Software description

`LayerFold` is a Python package released with the MIT Licence. It is available on a public GitHub repository, github.com/giomariapilo/layerfold, together with some tests and examples.

3.1. Software architecture

`LayerFold` is a Python library that leverages the PyTorch package to merge consecutive layers in a DNN into an equivalent one when the non-linearity between them degenerates. It is capable of folding the two primary types of layers that can be found in modern architectural designs. Its main functionality, `fold`, can automatically identify layers that can be combined, for Swin-T and ResNet architectures, and to fold them together. For other architectures, it is possible to use directly the functions `fuse_fc`, `fuse_conv`, and `fuse_conv_bn` to fuse two specific layers.

3.2. Software functionalities

This section describes more in detail the use of `LayerFold`. The two main functions are used to fuse fully connected layers and convolutional layers respectively.

Folding two fully connected layers is straightforward. In fact, when the nonlinearity of the first convolution, `fc1` degenerates, its output can be written as:

$$\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{x}W_1^T + b_1)W_2^T + b_2, \quad (1)$$

where $(\cdot)^T$ is the transpose operator. Rearranging the terms, \mathbf{y} can be equivalently viewed as the output of a single fully connected layer. The equivalent layer, `fceq` corresponds then to a fully connected layer of parameters $W_{eq} = W_2W_1$ and $b_{eq} = b_1W_2^T + b_2$.

Figure 2: Convolutional layers with multiple channels before merging.

Folding two convolutional layers implies that the output of **conv2**, y_2 , will then have c_2 channels and $n - k_1 - k_2 + 2$ dimension. The fusion of the two convolutional layers yields in this case an equivalent convolutional layer **conveq** of c_{in} input channels, c_2 output channels, and a kernel dimension of $k_1 + k_2 - 1$. Its weight tensor $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2 \times c_{in} \times (k_1 + k_2 - 1) \times (k_1 + k_2 - 1)}$ and its bias tensor, $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2}$, characterized as:

$$W_{eq} = W_1 * W_2 \quad (2)$$

$$b_{eq,j} = b_{2,j} + \sum_{i=1}^{c_1} b_{1,i} \sum_{l=1}^{k_2} \sum_{m=1}^{k_2} w_{2,i,j}. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 display how two convolutional layers look before and after the merging process.

3.3. Technical limitations

LayerFold presents some clear limitations when putting in practice layer collapse, as suggested by our theoretical analysis. When **conv2** presents a non-zero padding, folding is challenging. One potential approach we investigated

Figure 3: Convolutional layers with multiple channels after merging.

to address this challenge was to decouple the padding addition from **conv2** by representing it as a standalone operation (in Appendix A.4). Although extensions to some cases like having a stride higher than one in convolutional layers are straightforward, more studies on heterogeneous strides still need to be conducted. Besides, diverse typologies of convolutions, like dilated and grouped convolutions folding, are still under study. Moreover, although further solutions for merging padded layers like exploiting targeted knowledge distillation are in principle possible to provide a potentially acceptable approximation, it was chosen not to pursue them due to the analytical nature of the solutions we presented.

Despite the aforementioned limitations, we believe that the most commonly encountered scenarios were covered in this work, and updates for the **LayerFold** library will explore the missing cases under exam.

4. Illustrative examples

In this section, we will present some quantitative analysis for two of the most popular architectures, with some of their layers folded, and evaluated on seven different devices (Table 1).

Architectures. We present some quantitative analysis based on two popular architectures: ResNet-18 and Swin-T Transformer. Given the restrictions described in Sec. 3.3, ResNet-18 required some modifications to its internal architecture. In the first basic block, the first convolution, had its stride reduced from 2 to 1. Moreover, to maintain the shapes of the intermediate signals, an average pooling layer was added after the second convolutional and before the downsampling block. In the second basic block, the two

Device	CUDA cores	Memory
NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080	2944	8GB
NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000	2034	8GB
NVIDIA Quadro P2000	1024	5GB
NVIDIA RTX A4500	7168	20GB
NVIDIA Jetson Nano	1024	8GB
Raspberry Pi 4	-	4GB
Intel Xeon E5-2640	-	16GB

Table 1: Devices used for the inference time tests.

convolutions, had their zero padding changed from 1 to 2 and 0 respectively to maintain the shapes of the intermediate signals.

Datasets. For our benchmarks, we have chosen four downstream datasets. CIFAR-10 [26] is a widely-used dataset in computer vision, consisting of 60k color images, each of size 32×32 pixels, distributed evenly across 10 distinct classes.

Tiny ImageNet [27] is another popular benchmark for evaluating computer vision algorithms, consisting of 200 different classes, each containing 500 training images and 50 validation images, totaling 100k training images and 10k validation images. Each image is a color image resized to 64×64 pixels. Tiny ImageNet is a downsized version of the larger ImageNet-1k dataset.

PACS and VLCS are datasets drawn from the DomainBed suite [28], considered a standard benchmark for evaluating domain adaptation and generalization in computer vision. The variability in style and representation among the domains challenges models to learn features that generalize well across different visual appearances. In both cases, the images are resized to 224×224 pixels.

Layer collapse algorithm. To obtain models with collapsable layers, the method described in [11] was applied to the trained models. This strategy iteratively makes layers foldable by removing the non-linearity between them, at the cost of a negligible (or null) decrease in accuracy. After removing a number of ReLUs, the layers before and after them were fused together with our method. Since a closed-form solution was used, the accuracy of the models stayed the same. We highlight that there is no restriction on the method to employ for collapsing layers provided it replaces the nonlinearity with an identity function.

Metrics. To assess the computation gains through the layer collapse, we measure MFLOPs, the actual memory footprint of the model, and the inference time employing batch size equal to one. While the first is a theoretical

Figure 4: Comparison of FLOPs and model memory decreases slowly at first and then accelerates. (b) Swin-T shows a more uniform trend in both FLOPs and memory.

and deterministic measure, the last two are averaged over 100 inferences. Moreover, the accuracy of the model after each fusion is also evaluated, to ensure that it is unaffected by the fusion operation.

Devices. The inference time measures were taken across multiple CPU and GPU devices, in particular: five GPU-based devices the NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080, the NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000, the NVIDIA Quadro P2000, the NVIDIA RTX A4500, and the NVIDIA Jetson Orin- and 2 CPU- based ones -the Intel Xeon E5-2640, and the Raspberry Pi 4-. A summary of the in-devices CUDA cores availability and memory is provided in Table 1.

4.1. FLOPs and memory usage analysis

We present here a static analysis for both memory and number of operations, expressed in MFLOPs, for the collapsed ResNet-18 and Swin-T trained on CIFAR-10, from which we can remove up to five layers. We report our results in Fig. 4.

Looking at the results for ResNet-18 (Fig. 4a), removing the first layers decreases the memory occupation marginally, then, as more layers are removed, the decrease becomes steeper (for the fourth and the fifth layers). It is indeed possible that the first folded layers have a lower number of parameters compared to the last layers. Looking at the FLOPs, however, we can observe a dissimilar trend, lowering dramatically after the first layer is removed and then decreasing at a more modest rate as the model is compressed more. Evidently, memory and computation are interlinked but can show very different trends: thus, whether a layer folding method targets memory or computation reduction, it would drive a different choice for the layer(s) to remove.

Figure 5: Comparison of inference time gains in models trained on CIFAR10.

Although FLOPs are a theoretical measure, a match will be explored in later sections. The memory occupation will be similar for all the explored devices, given that the same libraries are employed.

4.2. Inference Time Measures

We present here an analysis of the measures conducted for the layer-folded architectures evaluated on the real devices, for a ResNet-18 model (Fig. 5a) and for Swin-T (Fig. 5b). For each model, we also present results obtained on all the tested datasets (in Appendix B). As a sanity check, we have validated that the performance of the model does not change as we fold layers 2.

Inferences of ResNet-18. While inference time across all devices and datasets generally decreases as more layers are removed, there are some notable exceptions. This is because folding layers results in convolutions with larger kernels, as observed in Appendix A.3, increasing the number of memory accesses. This phenomenon is evident in devices with limited memory and CUDA cores. Looking at the results for the NVIDIA RTX A4500, which is a device with a high number of CUDA cores (7168 cores), it is clear that this doesn't happen, compared to smaller devices such as the P2000 (1024 cores), the Quadro RTX 4000 (2304 cores) and the Jetson Orin (1024 cores). In many cases, we also observe large error bars, especially on resource-constrained devices working on large-size images (that is the case for the example of TinyInet), due to specific caching and memory latencies of the same device.

Inferences of Swin-T. The Swin-T inference times show a much more regular trend than the results observed for ResNet-18: removing layers results

Arch.	Dataset	Fused Layers					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
Resnet-18	CIFAR-10	91.51	91.51	91.51	91.51	91.51	91.51
	TinyInet	35.34	35.34	35.34	35.34	35.34	35.34
	PACS	93.50	93.50	93.50	93.50	93.50	-
	VLCS	91.79	91.79	91.79	91.79	91.79	-
Swin-T	CIFAR-10	92.17	92.17	92.17	-	-	-
	TinyInet	71.02	71.02	-	-	-	-
	PACS	99.40	99.40	99.40	-	-	-
	VLCS	96.27	96.27	-	-	-	-

Table 2: Accuracy of the models as layers are fused together. We put in bold the values corresponding to the maximum number of collapsable layers, according to [11].

in direct drop-in memory accesses as well since transformers are composed of fully connected layers, for which the computation effort is in general lower (when taken individually). Furthermore, this phenomenon tells us that removing specific layers can either lead to gains or losses in terms of computational time, and all the layer folding strategies should account more for these effects on the target hardware devices.

5. Impact

The current advancements in layer collapsing focus on removing the non linearities between layers, but very little work has been done on actually merging the layers to reduce the depth of the network. Until the layers are effectively removed, only minimal performance gains can be obtained. This might be critical for resource-constrained devices such as mobile phones which are becoming more and more important targets for machine learning applications.

LayerFold offers a simple, plug and play solution to actually implement the fusion on the trained network with no need for finetuning. This allowed in our case to perform a great number of measurements for multiple devices, including embedded ones. The results showed that removing layers does not always result in improvements in performance, revealing the need for further studies in this field. The ability to easily perform the merging of layers can be used for this and many future studies. Moreover, the simple implementation makes it easy to use even when employing other Machine Learning libraries. Since **LayerFold** only changes the layers inside a model, without any other modification to the structure, it is fully compatible with any other library.

6. Conclusions

In this work, we have contributed with `LayerFold`, a library that leverages the layer collapse phenomenon exploited by other works in the literature, providing all the mathematical tools to fuse fully connected and convolutional layers, respectively, in the absence of non-linearities. Throughout our analysis, we highlight the cases in which, in theory, a layer collapse is easily mappable to memory and computation savings, finding cases where this does not find an obvious solution (as described in Sec. 3.3). We evaluated the efficacy of layer merging on the most common architectures (ResNets and Transformers) deployed on real devices, assessing the resulting improvements in terms of memory and computational requirements. While the expected reductions in FLOPs and memory usage are observed, our results reveal different trends on specific hardware architectures, notably on edge devices such as Jetson Orin and Raspberry Pi 4. On these platforms, reducing the depth of deep architectures does not necessarily lead to improved computational efficiency and can even be detrimental. We observe that this outcome is attributed to memory transfers, which primarily affect large convolutional layers resulting from the layer’s folding operation.

This finding highlights a critical consideration for layer collapse methods, which often estimate theoretical improvements without accounting for device-specific constraints: the benefits in terms of actual computation times can be overwhelmed by high memory transfer rates. In addition, we have evidence that reducing computation complexity and memory occupation are not necessarily tightly interconnected and should be treated separately from design constraints, although synergistically.

By providing `LayerFold` open-source, we aim to facilitate further exploration in the layer collapse field and encourage research into alternative metrics, beyond FLOPs and DNN depth, that can be effectively reduced to improve model efficiency.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Giommaria Pilo: Methodology, Software, Writing - original draft. **Nour Hezbri:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft. **André Pereira e Ferreira:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft. **Victor Quéto:** Supervision. **Enzo Tartaglione:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to Liao Zhu for kindly providing opportunely modified and tested models for ResNet and Swin-T architectures together with his technical support and expertise.

References

- [1] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, G. Hinton, Deep Learning, *Nature* 521 (2015) 436–444. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>.
- [2] B. Kerbl, G. Kopanas, T. Leimkühler, G. Drettakis, 3D Gaussian Splatting for Real-Time Radiance Field Rendering, *ACM Transactions on Graphics* 42 (4) (July 2023).
- [3] F.-A. Croitoru, V. Hondru, R. T. Ionescu, M. Shah, Diffusion Models in Vision: A Survey, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis & Machine Intelligence* 45 (09) (2023) 10850–10869. doi:[10.1109/TPAMI.2023.3261988](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2023.3261988).
- [4] D. Khurana, A. Koli, K. Khatter, S. Singh, Natural language processing: State of the art, current trends and challenges, *Multimedia tools and applications* 82 (2023) 3713–3744. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-022-13428-4>.
- [5] A. Ben Abbes, J. Machicao, P. L. Corrêa, A. Specht, R. Devillers, J. P. Ometto, Y. Kondo, D. Mouillot, DeepWealth: A generalizable open-source deep learning framework using satellite images for well-being estimation, *SoftwareX* 27 (2024) 101785. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101785>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711024001560>
- [6] P. Gamallo-Fernandez, E. Rama-Maneiro, J. C. Vidal, M. Lama, VERONA: A python library for benchmarking deep learning in business process monitoring, *SoftwareX* 26 (2024) 101734. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101734>.

- URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711024001055>
- [7] F. Shama, A. Aziz, L. B. M. Deya, CitySolution: A complaining task distributive mobile application for smart city corporation using deep learning, *SoftwareX* 27 (2024) 101829. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2024.101829>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711024002000>
- [8] S. R. Dubey, S. K. Singh, B. B. Chaudhuri, Activation functions in deep learning: A comprehensive survey and benchmark, *Neurocomputing* 503 (2022) 92–108. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.06.111>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231222008426>
- [9] G. Menghani, Efficient Deep Learning: A Survey on Making Deep Learning Models Smaller, Faster, and Better, *ACM Comput. Surv.* 55 (12) (Mar. 2023). doi:[10.1145/3578938](https://doi.org/10.1145/3578938).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3578938>
- [10] B. La Rosa, G. Blasilli, R. Bourqui, D. Auber, G. Santucci, R. Capobianco, E. Bertini, R. Giot, M. Angelini, State of the Art of Visual Analytics for eXplainable Deep Learning, *Computer Graphics Forum* 42 (1) (2023) 319–355. arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/cgf.14733>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/cgf.14733>.
URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/cgf.14733>
- [11] Z. Liao, V. Quetu, V.-T. Nguyen, E. Tartaglione, Can Unstructured Pruning Reduce the Depth in Deep Neural Networks? , in: 2023 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW), IEEE Computer Society, Los Alamitos, CA, USA, 2023, pp. 1394–1398. doi:[10.1109/ICCVW60793.2023.00151](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCVW60793.2023.00151).
URL <https://doi.ieeecomputersociety.org/10.1109/ICCVW60793.2023.00151>
- [12] A. B. Dror, N. Zehngut, A. Raviv, E. Artyomov, R. Vitek, R. J. Jevnisek, Layer Folding: Neural Network Depth Reduction using Activation Linearization, in: *British Machine Vision Conference*, 2021.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:235458222>

- [13] N. K. Jha, Z. Ghodsi, S. Garg, B. Reagen, DeepReDuce: ReLU Reduction for Fast Private Inference, in: M. Meila, T. Zhang (Eds.), Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning, Vol. 139 of Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, PMLR, 2021, pp. 4839–4849.
URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v139/jha21a.html>
- [14] M. Cho, A. Joshi, B. Reagen, S. Garg, C. Hegde, Selective Network Linearization for Efficient Private Inference, in: K. Chaudhuri, S. Jegelka, L. Song, C. Szepesvari, G. Niu, S. Sabato (Eds.), Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning, Vol. 162 of Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, PMLR, 2022, pp. 3947–3961.
URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v162/cho22a.html>
- [15] Q. Bouniot, I. Redko, A. Mallasto, From Alexnet to Transformers: Measuring the Non-linearity of Deep Neural Networks with Affine Optimal Transport (9 2023). [arXiv:2310.11439](https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.11439).
- [16] G. Philipp Schoenherr, The Nonlinearity Coefficient-A Practical Guide to Neural Architecture Design, Ph.D. thesis, Carnegie Mellon University (2021). [arXiv:2105.12210](https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.12210).
- [17] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition, in: Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2016. [arXiv:1512.03385](https://arxiv.org/abs/1512.03385).
- [18] Z. Liu, Y. Lin, Y. Cao, H. Hu, Y. Wei, Z. Zhang, S. Lin, B. Guo, Swin Transformer: Hierarchical Vision Transformer Using Shifted Windows, in: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 2021, pp. 10012–10022.
- [19] V. Quéту, Z. Liao, E. Tartaglione, The Simpler The Better: An Entropy-Based Importance Metric to Reduce Neural Networks’ Depth, in: Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases. Research Track, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024, pp. 92–108.
- [20] Z. Liao, V. Quéту, V.-T. Nguyen, E. Tartaglione, Nepenthe: Entropy-based pruning as a neural network depth’s reducer, in: Submitted to The Thirteenth International Conference on Learning Representations, 2024, under review.
URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=fk5ePN7YCS>
- [21] S. Chen, Q. Zhao, Shallowing deep networks: Layer-wise pruning based on feature representations, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and

- Machine Intelligence 41 (12) (2019) 3048–3056. doi:10.1109/TPAMI.2018.2874634.
- [22] V. Quétu, N. Hezbri, E. Tartaglione, LaCoOT: Layer Collapse through Optimal Transport, arXiv preprint (2024). arXiv:2406.08933.
- [23] S. Liu, C. Zeng, L. Li, C. Yan, L. Fu, X. Mei, F. Chen, FoldGPT: Simple and Effective Large Language Model Compression Scheme, arXiv preprint (2024). arXiv:2407.00928.
- [24] L. Zhong, F. Wan, R. Chen, X. Quan, L. Li, BlockPruner: Fine-grained Pruning for Large Language Models, arXiv preprint (2024). arXiv:2406.10594.
- [25] C. H. Ali Mehmeti-Göpel, J. Disselhoff, Nonlinear Advantage: Trained Networks Might Not Be As Complex as You Think, in: Proceedings of the 40th International Conference on Machine Learning, Vol. 202 of Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, PMLR, 2023, pp. 529–546. URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v202/ali-mehmeti-gopel23a.html>
- [26] A. Krizhevsky, G. Hinton, Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images, Master’s thesis, Department of Computer Science, University of Toronto (2009).
- [27] Y. Le, X. Yang, Tiny imagenet visual recognition challenge, CS 231N 7 (7) (2015) 3.
- [28] I. Gulrajani, D. Lopez-Paz, In Search of Lost Domain Generalization, in: International Conference on Learning Representations, 2021. URL <https://openreview.net/forum?id=lQdXeXDwTl>

Appendix A. Mathematical derivations

In this section, we present a derivation of the folding method used to combine different layers together. Starting from the simplest case we explain how to fuse two fully connected layers, used when fusing layers inside Swin Transformers. Subsequently we present multiple cases for the fusion of convolutional layers for different numbers of input, output channels, and padding. As a disclaimer, our aim is not to provide a fully rigorous derivation of the method, but to give an intuition of the way this solution was obtained.

Appendix A.1. Fusing fully connected layers

Let **fc1** and **fc2** be two consecutive fully connected layers. let **fc1** have p input channels and q output channels, while **fc2** has q input channels and r output channels. They can be represented by their weights $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times p}$ and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times q}$, and their biases $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^q$ and $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^r$. Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ be the input of **fc1**, with dimensions n and p , and $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ the output of **fc2**, with dimensions n and r .

Let \mathbf{z} be the output of **fc1**, such that:

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{x}W_1^T + b_1. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The output \mathbf{y} of **fc2** is given by:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{z}W_2^T + b_2. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Combining A.1 with A.2, we get:

$$\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{x}W_1^T + b_1)W_2^T + b_2. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Similarly, the equation above can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x} (W_2W_1)^T + (b_1W_2^T + b_2). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

We then can identify a single fully connected layer **fceq**, equivalent to **fc1** and **fc2**, represented by the weight matrix $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times p}$ and the bias vector $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^r$.

$$W_{eq} = W_2W_1, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$b_{eq} = b_1W_2^T + b_2. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Substituting A.5 and A.6 into A.4 we get the equivalent fully connected layer **fceq**:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}W_{eq}^T + b_{eq}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Appendix A.2. Fusion of consecutive convolutional layers with square kernel, single input and output channels, unitary stride, and no padding

First, we start with a simple case: we consider two consecutive convolutional layers, **conv1** and **conv2**. The goal is to find a single convolutional layer **convec** that is equivalent to the two. To get an intuition on what is happening, we use a small example. Let both **conv1** and **conv2** have a square kernel with dimension 2, a single input and output channel, no padding and unitary stride.

Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 4 \times 4}$ be the input to **conv1** and $x_{i,j}$ be the element of x at the i -th row and j -th column. The matrix x is shown below:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} & x_{1,2} & x_{1,3} & x_{1,4} \\ x_{2,1} & x_{2,2} & x_{2,3} & x_{2,4} \\ x_{3,1} & x_{3,2} & x_{3,3} & x_{3,4} \\ x_{4,1} & x_{4,2} & x_{4,3} & x_{4,4} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Let $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 2}$ be the weight matrix of **conv1** and $w_{i,j}^1$ be the element of W_1 at the i -th row and j -th column. The matrix W_1 is:

$$W_1 = \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^1 & w_{1,2}^1 \\ w_{2,1}^1 & w_{2,2}^1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Let $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ be the bias vector of **conv1**. The output of **conv1** is $y_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 3 \times 3}$ such that:

$$y_1 = x \star W_1 + b_1, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where \star is the cross-correlation operator, which is the actual operation performed by the convolutional layer in deep learning frameworks and it is equivalent to:

$$x \star W_1 + b_1 = x * W_1^T + b_1, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

with $*$ being the convolution operator. The elements of y_1 are:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,1}^1 & y_{1,2}^1 & y_{1,3}^1 \\ y_{2,1}^1 & y_{2,2}^1 & y_{2,3}^1 \\ y_{3,1}^1 & y_{3,2}^1 & y_{3,3}^1 \end{bmatrix} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,2}w_{1,2}^1 + & \cdots & x_{1,3}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,4}w_{1,2}^1 + \\ x_{2,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1 & & x_{2,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1 \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ x_{3,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{1,2}^1 + & & x_{2,2}w_{3,3}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{1,2}^1 + \\ x_{4,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1 & \cdots & x_{4,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{A.12}
\end{aligned}$$

Let $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 2 \times 2}$ be the weight matrix of **conv2** and $w_{i,j}^2$ be the element of W_2 at the i -th row and j -th column. The matrix W_2 is:

$$W_2 = \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{2,1}^2 & w_{2,2}^2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{A.13}$$

Let $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ be the bias vector of **conv2**. The output of **conv2** is $y_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 2 \times 2}$ such that:

$$y_2 = y_1 \star W_2 + b_2. \tag{A.14}$$

The elements of y_2 are:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,1}^2 & y_{1,2}^2 \\ y_{2,1}^2 & y_{2,2}^2 \end{bmatrix} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 + y_{1,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + & y_{1,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 + y_{1,3}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + \\ y_{2,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + y_{2,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + b_2 & y_{2,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + y_{2,3}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + b_2 \\ y_{2,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 + y_{2,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + & y_{2,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 + y_{2,3}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + \\ y_{3,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + y_{3,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + b_2 & y_{3,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + y_{3,3}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + b_2 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{A.15}
\end{aligned}$$

Plugging equation A.12 into equation A.15, we get the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{1,1}^2 &= (x_{1,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,1}^2 + \\
&\quad (x_{1,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,2}^2 + \\
&\quad (x_{2,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,1}^2 + \\
&\quad (x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,2}^2 + b_2, \tag{A.16}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{1,2}^2 = & (x_{1,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{1,3}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,4}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,2}^2 + \\
& (x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{2,3}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,2}^2 + b_2,
\end{aligned} \tag{A.17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{2,1}^2 = & (x_{2,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,2}^2 + \\
& (x_{3,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{4,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{3,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,2}^2 + b_2,
\end{aligned} \tag{A.18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_{2,2}^2 = & (x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{2,3}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{1,2}^2 + \\
& (x_{3,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,1}^2 + \\
& (x_{3,3}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{4,4}w_{2,2}^1 + b_1) w_{2,2}^2 + b_2.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.19}$$

Since each element of y_1 is long, elements are shown separately and not in matrix form. Now, we can rewrite equations A.16, A.17, A.18 and A.19 by combining the weights that multiply the inputs $x_{i,j}$ and the biases b_1 and b_2 into a single weight matrix $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 3 \times 3}$ and a single bias vector $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$, respectively. The elements of W_{eq} and b_{eq} are:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_{eq} = & \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^{eq} & w_{1,2}^{eq} & w_{1,3}^{eq} \\ w_{2,1}^{eq} & w_{2,2}^{eq} & w_{2,3}^{eq} \\ w_{3,1}^{eq} & w_{3,2}^{eq} & w_{3,3}^{eq} \end{bmatrix} \\
= & \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{1,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{1,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,1}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{1,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 & w_{1,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{2,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{2,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 & w_{2,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{2,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 & w_{2,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.20}$$

By analyzing the elements of W_{eq} , we see that it is exactly the result of the convolution between W_1 and W_2 . The expression is shown below, where $*$ is the convolution operator:

$$W_{eq} = W_1 * W_2. \quad (\text{A.21})$$

The bias vector b_{eq} is the result of the sum of the bias vector of the second layer and the bias vector of the first layer multiplied by the sum of the elements of the second kernel:

$$b_{eq} = b_1 (w_{1,1}^2 + w_{1,2}^2 + w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,2}^2) + b_2 = b_1 \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 w_{i,j}^2 + b_2. \quad (\text{A.22})$$

In order to verify it is possible to generalize this result, let's consider the case where the input is $x \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 4 \times 4}$, **conv1** has a weight tensor $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 3 \times 3}$ and bias $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$, and **conv2** has a weight tensor $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 2 \times 2}$ and bias $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ as before. The input matrix x is displayed below:

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} & x_{1,2} & x_{1,3} & x_{1,4} \\ x_{2,1} & x_{2,2} & x_{2,3} & x_{2,4} \\ x_{3,1} & x_{3,2} & x_{3,3} & x_{3,4} \\ x_{4,1} & x_{4,2} & x_{4,3} & x_{4,4} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.23})$$

The weight matrix W_1 is:

$$W_1 = \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^1 & w_{1,2}^1 & w_{1,3}^1 \\ w_{2,1}^1 & w_{2,2}^1 & w_{2,3}^1 \\ w_{3,1}^1 & w_{3,2}^1 & w_{3,3}^1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Applying the equation A.10, we get the output $y_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 2 \times 2}$, which is displayed below:

$$y_1 = \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,1}^1 & y_{1,2}^1 \\ y_{2,1}^1 & y_{2,2}^1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$y_{1,1}^1 = x_{1,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,3}^1 + x_{2,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,3}^1 + x_{3,1}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1, \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$y_{1,2}^1 = x_{1,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{1,4}w_{1,3}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{2,3}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1, \quad (\text{A.27})$$

$$y_{2,1}^1 = x_{2,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,3}^1 + x_{3,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,3}^1 + x_{4,1}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1, \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$y_{2,2}^1 = x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{1,3}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{2,3}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{4,4}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1. \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Due to each element's length, they are shown separately and not in matrix form. Applying the equation A.14, we get the output $y_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times 1}$, which is displayed below:

$$y_2 = [y_{1,1}^2] = [y_{1,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 + y_{1,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + y_{2,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + y_{2,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + b_2], \quad (\text{A.30})$$

$$y_{1,1}^2 = \begin{aligned} & \left(\begin{array}{l} x_{1,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,3}^1 + \\ x_{2,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,3}^1 + \\ x_{3,1}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1 \end{array} \right) w_{1,1}^2 + \\ & \left(\begin{array}{l} x_{1,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{1,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{1,4}w_{1,3}^1 + \\ x_{2,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{2,3}^1 + \\ x_{3,2}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1 \end{array} \right) w_{1,2}^2 + \\ & \left(\begin{array}{l} x_{2,1}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,2}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,3}^1 + \\ x_{3,1}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,2}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,3}^1 + \\ x_{4,1}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{4,2}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1 \end{array} \right) w_{2,1}^2 + \\ & \left(\begin{array}{l} x_{2,2}w_{1,1}^1 + x_{2,3}w_{1,2}^1 + x_{2,4}w_{1,3}^1 + \\ x_{3,2}w_{2,1}^1 + x_{3,3}w_{2,2}^1 + x_{3,4}w_{2,3}^1 + \\ x_{4,2}w_{3,1}^1 + x_{4,3}w_{3,2}^1 + x_{4,4}w_{3,3}^1 + b_1 \end{array} \right) w_{2,2}^2 + b_2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

Now, we can rewrite equation A.31 by combining the weights that multiply the inputs $x_{i,j}$ and the biases b_1 and b_2 into a single weight matrix $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 4 \times 4}$, and a single bias vector $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$, respectively. The elements of W_{eq} and b_{eq} are displayed below:

$$W_{eq} = \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{1,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{1,3}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,3}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{1,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,1}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{1,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{2,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{1,3}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{2,3}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{1,3}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{2,3}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{2,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{3,1}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{2,1}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{2,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{3,1}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{3,2}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{2,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{2,3}^1 w_{2,1}^2 + w_{3,2}^1 w_{1,2}^2 + w_{3,3}^1 w_{1,1}^2 & w_{2,3}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{3,3}^1 w_{1,2}^2 \\ w_{3,1}^1 w_{2,1}^2 & w_{3,1}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{3,2}^1 w_{2,1}^2 & w_{3,2}^1 w_{2,2}^2 + w_{3,3}^1 w_{2,1}^2 & w_{3,3}^1 w_{2,2}^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.32})$$

$$b_{eq} = b_1 (w_{1,1}^2 + w_{1,2}^2 + w_{2,1}^2 + w_{2,2}^2) + b_2 = b_1 \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 w_{i,j}^2 + b_2. \quad (\text{A.33})$$

Once again, by analyzing the elements of W_{eq} , we can see that it is exactly the result of the convolution between W_1 and W_2 . The expression of b_{eq} is the same as before, as well. Therefore, the result is generalizable to any input size. The following paragraph summarizes this result.

Let's consider two consecutive convolutional layers, **conv1** and **conv2**, both with square kernels, unitary stride, and no padding. Let **conv1** be a convolutional layer with one input channel, one output channel, and kernel dimension k_1 ; therefore it will have a weight tensor $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times k_1 \times k_1}$ and a bias $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$. In a similar way, let **conv2** be a convolutional layer with one input channel, one output channel, and kernel dimension k_2 ; therefore it will have a weight tensor $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times k_2 \times k_2}$ and a bias $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$. Let x be the input of **conv1** with one channel and both dimensions equal to n such that $x \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n \times n}$. The output of **conv2** will then have one channel and dimensions $n - k_1 - k_2 + 2$. The equivalent single convolutional layer **convec** has the weight matrix $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1 \times (k_1 + k_2 - 1) \times (k_1 + k_2 - 1)}$ and the bias vector $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ such that:

$$W_{eq} = W_1 * W_2, \quad (\text{A.34})$$

$$b_{eq} = b_1 \sum_{i=1}^{k_2} \sum_{j=1}^{k_2} w_{i,j}^2 + b_2, \quad (\text{A.35})$$

where $*$ is the convolution operator. The result is generalizable to any input size, within the restriction stated above.

Appendix A.3. Fusion of consecutive convolutional layers with square kernel, multiple input and output channels, unitary stride, and no padding

After the simple case of two convolutions with a single input and output channel, we discuss a more complex situation. Consider the case where **conv1** and **conv2** are two consecutive convolution operations with multiple input and output channels, square kernels, unitary stride, and no padding.

Let **conv1** be a convolutional layer with c_{in} input channels, c_1 output channels, and kernel dimension k_1 ; therefore it will have a weight tensor $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{c_1 \times c_{in} \times k_1 \times k_1}$ and a bias $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{c_1 \times 1}$. In a similar way, let **conv2** be a convolutional layer with c_1 input channels, c_2 output channels, and kernel dimension k_2 ; therefore it will have a weight tensor $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2 \times c_1 \times k_2 \times k_2}$ and a bias $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2 \times 1}$. Let x be the input of **conv1** with c_{in} channels and both dimensions equal to n such that $x \in \mathbb{R}^{c_{in} \times n \times n}$. The output of **conv2** will then have one channel and dimensions $n - k_1 - k_2 + 2$. The equivalent single convolutional layer **conveq** has the weight matrix $W_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2 \times c_{in} \times (k_1+k_2-1) \times (k_1+k_2-1)}$ and the bias vector $b_{eq} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_2 \times 1}$. Notice that the weight tensors' first dimension is the number of output channels c_2 , and the second dimension is the number of input channels c_{in} .

Since the complexity of this case is much higher than the previous case, the figure 2 shows a diagram of the tensors involved in each calculation step. In this situation, we have chosen as the input tensor $x \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 5 \times 5}$, as the first weight tensors $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3}$, as second weight tensor $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 2}$, and as the bias vectors $b_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ and $b_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 1}$. The output tensor will be $y_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 2 \times 2}$.

Each channel of the input tensor x has been called x_i , where i is the channel index. Each kernel of the respective weight tensors W_1 and W_2 has been called K_{ij}^l , where l is the convolutional layer index, i is the input channel index, and j is the output channel. Each channel of the intermediate tensor y_1 has been called y_i^1 , whereas each channel of the output tensor y_2 has been called y_i^2 , where i is the channel index. The bias vectors b_i have elements b_i^l , where l is the convolutional layer index and i is the channel index.

With this information, we can write the value of the one-dimensional vector $y_1 = (y_1^1, y_2^1, y_3^1)^T$ as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1^1 \\ y_2^1 \\ y_3^1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \star K_{11}^1 + x_2 \star K_{21}^1 + x_3 \star K_{31}^1 + b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \\ x_1 \star K_{12}^1 + x_2 \star K_{22}^1 + x_3 \star K_{32}^1 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \\ x_1 \star K_{13}^1 + x_2 \star K_{23}^1 + x_3 \star K_{33}^1 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.36})$$

In a similar way, we can write the value of the one-dimensional vector $y_2 = (y_1^2, y_2^2, y_3^2, y_4^2)^T$ as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1^2 \\ y_2^2 \\ y_3^2 \\ y_4^2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_1^1 \star K_{11}^2 + y_2^1 \star K_{21}^2 + y_3^1 \star K_{31}^2 + b_1^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \\ y_1^1 \star K_{12}^2 + y_2^1 \star K_{22}^2 + y_3^1 \star K_{32}^2 + b_2^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \\ y_1^1 \star K_{13}^2 + y_2^1 \star K_{23}^2 + y_3^1 \star K_{33}^2 + b_3^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \\ y_1^1 \star K_{14}^2 + y_2^1 \star K_{24}^2 + y_3^1 \star K_{34}^2 + b_4^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.37})$$

Now, using the result obtained in A.21, we can replace the value of y_1 from equation A.36 into equation A.37, which results in:

$$\begin{aligned} y_1^2 = & x_1 \star (K_{11}^1 \star K_{11}^2 + K_{12}^1 \star K_{21}^2 + K_{13}^1 \star K_{31}^2) + \\ & x_2 \star (K_{21}^1 \star K_{11}^2 + K_{22}^1 \star K_{21}^2 + K_{23}^1 \star K_{31}^2) + \\ & x_3 \star (K_{31}^1 \star K_{11}^2 + K_{32}^1 \star K_{21}^2 + K_{33}^1 \star K_{31}^2) + \\ & (b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{11}^2 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{21}^2 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{31}^2) + b_1^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{aligned}, \quad (\text{A.38})$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_2^2 = & x_1 \star (K_{11}^1 \star K_{12}^2 + K_{12}^1 \star K_{22}^2 + K_{13}^1 \star K_{32}^2) + \\ & x_2 \star (K_{21}^1 \star K_{12}^2 + K_{22}^1 \star K_{22}^2 + K_{23}^1 \star K_{32}^2) + \\ & x_3 \star (K_{31}^1 \star K_{12}^2 + K_{32}^1 \star K_{22}^2 + K_{33}^1 \star K_{32}^2) + \\ & (b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{12}^2 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{22}^2 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{32}^2) + b_2^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{aligned}, \quad (\text{A.39})$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_3^2 = & x_1 \star (K_{11}^1 \star K_{13}^2 + K_{12}^1 \star K_{23}^2 + K_{13}^1 \star K_{33}^2) + \\ & x_2 \star (K_{21}^1 \star K_{13}^2 + K_{22}^1 \star K_{23}^2 + K_{23}^1 \star K_{33}^2) + \\ & x_3 \star (K_{31}^1 \star K_{13}^2 + K_{32}^1 \star K_{23}^2 + K_{33}^1 \star K_{33}^2) + \\ & (b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{13}^2 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{23}^2 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{33}^2) + b_3^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{aligned}, \quad (\text{A.40})$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_4^2 = & x_1 \star (K_{11}^1 \star K_{14}^2 + K_{12}^1 \star K_{24}^2 + K_{13}^1 \star K_{34}^2) + \\ & x_2 \star (K_{21}^1 \star K_{14}^2 + K_{22}^1 \star K_{24}^2 + K_{23}^1 \star K_{34}^2) + \\ & x_3 \star (K_{31}^1 \star K_{14}^2 + K_{32}^1 \star K_{24}^2 + K_{33}^1 \star K_{34}^2) + \\ & (b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{14}^2 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{24}^2 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{34}^2) + b_4^2 \mathbb{1}_{2 \times 2} \end{aligned}. \quad (\text{A.41})$$

By analyzing the four equations above, we can notice that, for each component y_j^2 , we have a linear combination of the inputs x_i , with coefficients given

by the sum of the convolution of a subset of the kernels K_{ij}^l and a bias term that does not depend on the input, as expected. We are going to call each kernel that multiplies the input x_j as K_{ij}^{eq} . Thus, the equations from A.38 to A.41 can be rewritten as:

$$y_j^2 = x_1 \star K_{1j}^{eq} + x_2 \star K_{2j}^{eq} + x_3 \star K_{3j}^{eq} + b_j^{eq}, \quad (\text{A.42})$$

where K_{ij}^{eq} is the kernel that operates on the input x_j and b_j^{eq} is the bias term that does not depend on the input. The expressions for K_{ij}^{eq} and b_j^{eq} are displayed below:

$$K_{ij}^{eq} = K_{i1}^1 \star K_{1j}^2 + K_{i2}^1 \star K_{2j}^2 + K_{i3}^1 \star K_{3j}^2, \quad (\text{A.43})$$

$$b_j^{eq} = b_1^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{1j}^2 + b_2^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{2j}^2 + b_3^1 \mathbb{1}_{3 \times 3} \star K_{3j}^2 + b_j^2. \quad (\text{A.44})$$

Additionally, we can see that these sums can be rewritten as a function of the number of input channels c_{in} , output channels c_1 of **conv1** and output channels c_2 of **conv2**. Rewriting the equations A.43 and A.44, we have:

$$K_{ij}^{eq} = \sum_{k=1}^{c_1} K_{ik}^1 \star K_{kj}^2, \quad (\text{A.45})$$

$$b_j^{eq} = b_j^2 + b_i^1 \sum_{k=1}^{k_2} \sum_{l=1}^{k_2} K_{ijkl}^2. \quad (\text{A.46})$$

To calculate all the equivalent parameters, the algorithm 1 has been implemented into PyTorch.

Algorithm 1 Convolutional Equation Update

```

for  $j = 1, 2, \dots, c_2$  do
  for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, c$  do
     $K_{ij}^{eq} \leftarrow \sum_{k=1}^{c_1} K_{ik}^1 \star K_{kj}^2$ 
  end for
   $b_j^{eq} \leftarrow b_j^2 + b_i^1 \sum_{k=1}^{k_2} \sum_{l=1}^{k_2} K_{ijkl}^2$ 
end for

```

*Appendix A.4. Folding convolutional layers with padding in **conv2**.*

One potential approach we investigated to address this challenge was to decouple the padding addition from **conv2** by representing it as a standalone operation. This can be achieved by leveraging the transposed convolution operator with unitary input and output channels, and a unitary stride, where

the corresponding kernel K has dimension $2p + 1 \times 2p + 1$, with p denoting the padding size. Specifically, it will have only one element to one (at his center) while having all the rest of his parameters to zero, according to:

$$K_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j = p \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.47})$$

The transposed convolution operation writes then as:

$$\mathbf{y}_1 = \mathbf{y}_1^{\text{padded}} * K \quad (\text{A.48})$$

We can study this kernel by applying the discrete Fourier transform operation which we denote \mathcal{F} . Let us write here below the expression for the particular case of padding $p = 1$ to alleviate the notations:

$$\mathcal{F}(K)_{kl} = \exp \left[-i2\pi \frac{(k+l)}{3} \right], \quad (\text{A.49})$$

where $k, l \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Our ultimate goal is here to fold the transposed convolution to incorporate the padding with the convolution operator. Therefore, we seek to invert the kernel K : the inverse, if it exists, would write

$$K^{-1} = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\{\text{inverse}[\mathcal{F}(K)]\}. \quad (\text{A.50})$$

However, the determinant of the tensor $\mathcal{F}(K)$ reveals a value of 0. This result captures the non-injectivity of the transformation encoded by the Fourier transform, implying that multiple distinct temporal domain signals can map to the same representation in the frequency domain. Furthermore, we try to resort to the pseudo-inverse, namely

$$\mathcal{F}(K)^* \mathcal{F}(K) = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 3e^{-i2\pi/3} & 3e^{i2\pi/3} \\ 3e^{i2\pi/3} & 3 & 3e^{-i2\pi/3} \\ 3e^{-i2\pi/3} & 3e^{i2\pi/3} & 3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.51})$$

where $(\cdot)^*$ is the conjugate transpose operator. Subsequently, we compute a numerical approximation of the pseudoinverse, followed by the application of the inverse Fourier transform. This unfortunately yields a complex-valued tensor, for which retaining only the real part results overall in a significant loss of information. This again underscores the non-invertibility and input dependence inherent in this setup, rendering its fusion an open research question for future exploration.

Appendix B. Additional results

